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Determination of Genetic Diversity of Local Chickens in Sanliurfa region using RAPD-PCR Method

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Abstract

In this study, the phylogenetic structures of village chickens in Sanliurfa region were determined by molecular techniques. Chickens traditionally raised in the villages of province constitute the animal material of this study. Determining the variation at the DNA level of local farm animals is of great importance for the identification, protection and development of genetic resources in animal husbandry. This study is expected to determine the genetic diversity in Sanliurfa region native chickens by RAPD-PCR method and to contribute to the molecular genetic knowledge and literature on chickens that have been traditionally raised for many years. The means of the observed allele number (na), effective allele number (ne), gene diversity (h) and Shannon information index (I) values for the chicken population from which the samples were taken were found to be 1.5385±0.1224, 1.4627±0.1079, 0.2472±0.0567 and 0.0827, respectively.

Key Words: Chicken, mtDNA, phylogenetics

INTRODUCTION

Livestock farming has an important place in agricultural income. In recent years, methods introduced in the field of molecular genetics to develop different genotypes have made it possible to determine and utilize the genetic structures of various farm animal populations at the DNA level. There are many methods based on the amplification of DNA fragments using PCR (Polymerase Chain Reaction). Almost all of the methods work on the basis of PCR. The most widely used ones of these methods are RFLP (Restriction Fragment Length Polymorphism), Microsatellite, SNP (Single nucleotide polymorphism) and RAPD (Randomly Amplified Polymorphic DNA). These techniques are widely used in fields such as biology, agriculture, medicine, veterinary medicine, forestry and fisheries. These methods have now begun to be used in the field of animal breeding and genetics and genetic variations within and between breeds can be determined. Molecular techniques are used to determine the genetic structure in populations, marker-assisted selection (MAS) studies, genetic maps, phylogenetic analyses, parentage and sex determination, diagnosis of some diseases, etc.

RAPD-PCR (Random Amplified Polymorphic DNA-PCR) method, randomly prepared primers (10 bases long) without the need for nucleotide sequence information and without any specific criteria in base order, it is a molecular method based on the adhesion of DNA to regions that may be symmetrical in the genome under study and the amplification of these regions by PCR technique (Williams et al., 1990). It is widely used because it is a simpler, relatively cheaper and less labor-intensive method compared to other polymorphism methods. The RAPD method (Williams et al., 1990) has been used as a genetic marker in

many farm animal species such as cattle (Kantanen et al., 1995; Cerit, 2001), goat (Li et al., 2002; Sahin, 2005), chicken (Wei et al., 1997; Sharma et al., 2001), turkey (Smith et al., 1996), quail (Yeğenoğlu, 1999; Sharma et al., 2000) and sheep (Kantanen et al., 1995; Cushwa et al., 1996; Tahmoorespur et al., 2003).

Smith et al., (1996), in their study with chickens and turkeys, found that the genetic distance between species was higher than within species and reported that the RAPD technique was an effective method for determining genetic relationships within and between different poultry populations. In many studies conducted using the RAPD method in chickens to determine genetic diversity. It was determined that genetic similarity values within populations were high, and genetic similarity values between populations were low. Sharma et al., (2001) Romanov and Weigend (2001). Molecular genetic studies for the identification, protection and development of genetic resources need to be intensified. The aim of this study is to investigate the genetic diversity of native chickens in the Şanlıurfa region by RAPD-PCR method and to contribute to the literature and molecular genetic knowledge about native chickens from our farm animals.

MATERIALS and METHODS

In this study, DNA material consisted of DNA samples isolated from local village chickens in the Şanlıurfa region and preserved in the Animal Biotechnology Laboratory. Genomic DNA was isolated from chickens using a DNA isolation kit (GeneJET Whole Blood Genomic DNA Purification Mini Kit #K0781, Thermo). Information on the primers to be used in the RAPD-PCR analysis study is given in Table 1.

Table 1. RAPD primers

Order	Name	Sequence (5' to 3')	bp	Tm (°C)	GC rate (%)
1	RAPD-OPE-01	CCCAAGGTCC	10	34	70
2	RAPD-OPE-02	GGTGCGGGAA	10	34	70
3	RAPD-OPE-05	TCAGGGAGGT	10	32	60
4	RAPD-OPE-06	AAGACCCCTC	10	32	60
5	RAPD-OPA-16	AGCCAGCGAA	10	32	60
6	RAPD-OPA-18	AGGTGACCGT	10	32	60
7	RAPD-OPA-19	CAAACGTCGG	10	32	60
8	RAPD-OPA-20	GTTGCGATCC	10	32	60

The PCR mixture to be used in amplification with the polymerase chain reaction technique is shown in Table 2.

Table 2. PCR mix

Components	Concentration	Amount
Kalıp DNA	20-30 ng/µl	1.0 µl
PCR Buffer	10X	2.0 µl
RAPD Primer	20 pmol/µl	1.0 µl
dNTP mix	1.0 nM	1.0 µl
Taq DNA polimeraz	5U/µl	0.5 µl
dH ₂ O		15.0 µl
Total		20.0 µl

After all of these components were prepared in the specified amounts in 0.2 ml PCR Eppendorf tubes on dry ice, they were placed in the device with pre-programmed PCR conditions.

The PCR amplification conditions used in the amplification of the studied gene region by the polymerase chain reaction technique are given in Table 3.

Table 3. PCR amplification conditions

Loop operation	Temperature (°C)	Number of loops	Duration
Pre-denaturation	95	1	4 dakika
Denaturation	94	} 35	60 sekond
Adhesion (T _m)	32-35		60 sekond
Synthesis	72		2 minute
Final elongation	72	1	10 minute
Waiting	4	∞	∞

PCR studies were performed in a Boeco (Germany) brand thermocycler device with gradient feature. 2% agarose gel was used to visualize the PCR products to be amplified (2 g agarose/100 ml 1XTBE). 100 bp ladder (Fermentas) was used as a marker in running PCR gels. RAPD band evaluation process: The

lengths of the bands in the gel were determined based on the length marker (100 bp). A data matrix was then created to evaluate the bands based on their presence in the gel, assigning a value of 1 if the band was present and 0 otherwise. Calculations were made in the POPGEN32 Ver. 1.33 (Yeh, 1999) package program. The dendrogram for the populations was created according to the UPGMA (Unweighted pair method with arithmetic mean) method. Genetic dendrograms and genetic distance values between samples were determined using the web-based Dendro-UPGMA program. Genetic similarity between individuals was calculated according to the Nei method (Nei and Li, 1979).

RESULTS and DISCUSSION

Genomic DNA was isolated from chickens using a DNA isolation kit and agarose gel images of isolated DNAs are given in Figure 1.

Figure 1. DNAs (01-18) isolated from chickens (1 kb ladder)

RAPD bands detected in chicken DNA samples are given in Figure 2.

Figure 2. Bands of RAPD primers

Polymorphic bands were obtained from RAPD primers OPE-01, OPA-16, OPE06 and OPA-20. Polymorphism could not be detected since similar band patterns were seen in all samples with the OPE-05 primer. Other primers OPE-02, OPA-018 and OPA-19 did not produce enough bands to be evaluated in all samples. However, with the OPE-01 primer, 3 alleles (OPE-01-1, OPE01-2, OPE-01-3) and a total of 47 bands were detected in the range of approximately 400-1200 bp. OPE-01 primer allele frequencies are given in Table 4.

Table 4. Allele frequencies for all loci in chickens

Primers	Number of Bands	Frequencies	
		Allele 0	Allele 1
OPE-01	OPE-01-1	0.6236	0.3764
	OPE-01-2	-	1.0000
	OPE-01-3	-	1.0000
OPA-16	OPA-16-1	-	1.0000
	OPA-16-2	-	1.0000
	OPA-16-3	0.5774	0.4082
	OPA-16-4	0.4226	0.5918
OPE-06	OPE-06-1	-	1.0000
	OPE-06-2	-	1.0000
	OPE-06-3	0.2357	0.7643
OPA-20	OPA-20-1	0.5270	0.4730
	OPA-20-2	0.6667	0.3333
	OPA-20-3	0.6236	0.3764

Here, the 0-allele frequency of OPE-01-1 was calculated as 0.6236 and the 1 allele frequency as 0.3764. With the OPA-016 primer, 4 alleles (OPA-16-1, OPA-16-2, OPA-16-3, OPA-16-4) and a total of 63 bands were detected in the range of approximately 200-1500 bp. Here, the 0 allele frequencies of OPA-16-3 and OPA-16-4 were calculated as 0.5774 and 0.4226, and the 1 allele frequencies were calculated as 0.4082 and 0.5918, respectively. With the OPE-06 primer, 3 alleles (OPE-06-1, OPE06-2, OPE-06-3) and a total of 28 bands were detected in the range of approximately 800-1500 bp. OPE-06 primer allele frequencies are given in Table 4. Here, the 0-allele frequency of OPE-06-3 was calculated as 0.2357 and the 1 allele frequency as 0.7043. With the OPA-020 primer, 3 alleles (OPA-020-1, OPA-020-2, OPA-020-3) and a total of 40 bands were detected in the range of approximately 500-1200 bp. OPA-20 primer allele frequencies are given in Table 4. Here, the 0 allele frequencies of OPA-020-1, OPA-020-2, OPA-020-3 were calculated as 0.5270, 0.6667 and 0.6236, and the 1 allele frequencies were calculated as 0.4730, 0.3333 and 0.3764, respectively. With the OPE-05 primer, 4 alleles (OPE-05-1, OPE05-2, OPE-05-3, OPE-05-4) and a total of 72 bands were detected in the range of approximately 600-2000 bp. Since similar bands were seen in all samples, polymorphism could not be detected with the OPE-05 primer.

For genetic calculations in chickens, a data matrix was created with polymorphic bands of OPE-01, OPA-16, OPE-06 and OPA-20 primers. The observed allele number (na), effective number of alleles (ne), gene diversity (h) and Shannon information index (I) values of the alleles of the relevant primers were calculated and are given in Table 5. For the chicken population, the mean values of observed allele number (na), effective number of alleles (ne), gene diversity (h) and Shannon information index (I) were found to be 1.5385 ± 0.1224 , 1.4627 ± 0.1079 , 0.2472 ± 0.0567 and 0.0827, respectively.

Table 5. Genetic diversity statistics for all loci in chickens

Lokus	n	na	ne	h	I
OPE-01-1	18	2.0000	1.8848	0.4694	0.6623
OPE-01-2	18	1.0000	1.0000	0.0000	0.0000
OPE-01-3	18	1.0000	1.0000	0.0000	0.0000
OPA-16-1	18	1.0000	1.0000	0.0000	0.0000
OPA-16-2	18	1.0000	1.0000	0.0000	0.0000
OPA-16-3	18	2.0000	1.9533	0.4880	0.6811
OPA-16-4	18	2.0000	1.9348	0.4832	0.6762
OPE-06-1	18	1.0000	1.0000	0.0000	0.0000
OPE-06-2	18	1.0000	1.0000	0.0000	0.0000
OPE-06-3	18	2.0000	1.5632	0.3603	0.5461
OPA-20-1	18	2.0000	1.9942	0.4985	0.6917
OPA-20-2	18	2.0000	1.8000	0.4444	0.6365
OPA-20-3	18	2.0000	1.8848	0.4694	0.6623
Mean	18	1.5385	1.4627	0.2472	0.3505
St. Dev.		0.5189	0.4574	0.2405	0.3395

(na: number of alleles observed, ne: effective number of alleles, h: gene diversity, I: Shannon information index) Number of polymorphic loci: 7, Polymorphic locus: %53.85

Genetic distance values for the chicken population are given in Table 6. Genetic distances were calculated between 0.000-0.615. When Table 6 is examined in terms of genetic distances between chickens, the existence of genetic diversity is seen.

Table 6. Genetic distances among chickens

	a1	a2	a3	a4	a5	a6	a7	a8	a9	a10	a11	a12	a13	a14	a15	a16	a17	a18
a1	0	0.100	0.100	0.100	0.308	0.385	0.250	0.167	0.333	0.000	0.182	0.300	0.308	0.250	0.231	0.385	0.385	0.167
a2		0	0.000	0.000	0.250	0.333	0.333	0.250	0.417	0.100	0.273	0.400	0.385	0.333	0.308	0.462	0.333	0.250
a3			0	0.000	0.250	0.333	0.333	0.250	0.417	0.100	0.273	0.400	0.385	0.333	0.308	0.462	0.333	0.250
a4				0	0.250	0.333	0.333	0.250	0.417	0.100	0.273	0.400	0.385	0.333	0.308	0.462	0.333	0.250
a5					0	0.083	0.231	0.154	0.308	0.308	0.308	0.538	0.154	0.231	0.077	0.231	0.083	0.154
a6						0	0.308	0.231	0.250	0.385	0.250	0.500	0.083	0.167	0.154	0.167	0.167	0.231
a7							0	0.083	0.250	0.250	0.250	0.500	0.231	0.308	0.154	0.167	0.167	0.083
a8								0	0.167	0.167	0.167	0.417	0.154	0.231	0.077	0.231	0.231	0.000
a9									0	0.333	0.182	0.300	0.167	0.250	0.231	0.250	0.385	0.167
a10										0	0.182	0.300	0.308	0.250	0.231	0.385	0.385	0.167
a11											0	0.300	0.167	0.250	0.231	0.250	0.385	0.167
a12												0	0.417	0.364	0.462	0.500	0.615	0.417
a13													0	0.083	0.077	0.083	0.231	0.154
a14														0	0.154	0.167	0.308	0.231
a15															0	0.154	0.154	0.077
a16																0	0.167	0.231
a17																	0	0.231
a18																		0

The UPGMA genetic tree created with the genetic distance values of the chicken population is given in Figure 4. When Figure 4 is examined, it is seen that it is divided into 5 clusters as {a12}, {a2-a3-a4-a1-a10}, {a16-a14-a15-a5-a13-a6}, {a17-a7-a18-a8}, {a11-a9}.

Figure 3. UPGMA tree in chickens

In conclusion, polymorphisms and genetic relationships were determined using the RAPD-PCR technique in local chickens from the Şanlıurfa region. The research results are expected to contribute to genetic studies on chickens. Therefore, the results obtained are important for maintaining genetic diversity and genetic diversity among village chickens. In addition, the study results are expected to contribute to genetic

polymorphism and biodiversity studies, as well as national and international genetic resource conservation strategies.

Conflicts of Interest: The author(s) declare(s) that there is no conflict of interest regarding this work.

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